

THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE AND MODERN METHODS IN INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, we discuss the importance of creative and modern methods in increasing the effectiveness of education and how teachers help students to improve their skills, such as problem solving, critical thinking, and making connections between subjects. Why it is important to create a learning environment: helping students develop their creative capacities can have both direct and indirect benefits. How to use useful tools to increase students' interest in language and allow them to advance knowledge, academic skills, and personal skills.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishda ijodiy va zamonaviy usullarning ahamiyati va o'qituvchilarning o'quvchilarning muammoni yechish, tanqidiy fikrlash, fanlar o'rtasida aloqadorlik o'rnatish kabi malakalarini oshirishga qanday yordam berishi haqida gapiramiz. Ta'lim muhitini yaratish nima uchun muhim: o'quvchilarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga yordam berish bevosita va bilvosita foyda keltirishi mumkin. Talabalarning tilga qiziqishini oshirish va ularga bilim, akademik ko'nikmalar va shaxsiy ko'nikmalarni oshirishga imkon berish uchun foydali vositalardan qanday foydalanish kerak.

Аннотация: В этой статье мы обсуждаем важность творческих и современных методов в повышении эффективности образования и то, как учителя помогают ученикам улучшить свои навыки, такие как решение проблем, критическое мышление и установление связей между предметами. Почему важно создавать среду обучения: помощь учащимся в развитии творческих способностей может иметь как прямые, так и косвенные выгоды. Как использовать полезные инструменты, чтобы повысить интерес учащихся к языку и позволить им совершенствовать знания, академические навыки и личные навыки.

Key words: Modern methods, engagement, observe, cognitive skills, benefits, environment, ideas, approach to, error, provides options, learner-centered, connections.

Kalit so'zlar: Zamonaviy usullar, jalb qilish, kuzatish, kognitiv qobiliyatlar, foyda, muhit, g'oyalar, yondashuv, xato, variantlarni taqdim etadi, o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan, aloqalar.

Ключевые слова: Современные методы, участие, наблюдение, когнитивные навыки, преимущества, окружающая среда, идеи, подход, ошибки, предоставляют варианты, ориентированы на учащихся, связи

Introduction

Teachers who frequently assign classwork involving creativity are more likely to observe higher-order cognitive skills—problem solving, critical thinking, and making connections between subjects—in their students.

In addition, when teachers combine creativity with transformative technology use, they see even better outcomes. A creative learning environment is one that encourages students to learn through trial and error, their imagination, and to think critically to solve problems. A creative learning environment can help students

practice and develop their own theories, ideas and set them in motion.

Methods

Why is it important to foster a creative learning environment?

Helping students to develop their creative capacities can have both direct and indirect benefits. Rather than feeling penalized or embarrassed for taking chances, students can feel comfortable trying new things and making mistakes in a creative learning environment. As students are encouraged to pursue creative solutions to a problem, they can learn persistence in the process of continually trying a new approach to solve that problem. Additionally, students can also become better at:

Working as a team

Solving complex problems

Finding new ways to learn

Why do students need to be creative?

Being creative and putting these skills to use is crucial in today's environment, since creativity is becoming a more valued quality. One essential element of the varied thinking required for innovation is creativity. Expanding their creative capacity can make students more adept at forming original ideas as well as exercising their critical thinking skills. Creativity is also a life skill that can help students unlock new avenues in their personal self-expression.

By controlling the classroom environment where students spend hours each day, teachers have sample opportunities to nurture and cultivate creativity. In practice, that usually means two things: serving as a role model for students and finding ways to stimulate their creative thinking processes.

Although creativity can develop outside of the classroom, teachers play an indispensable role in maintaining and encouraging its continuous development.

There's no single recipe for developing creativity in students, but there are some simple things you can do to make your classroom a little more creative.

Many of the most effective ways to encourage creativity in a classroom environment are simple augmentations of existing practices. Others are as simple as learning to identify opportunities to help students exercise their creativity. For instance, some students could choose to study at their desks, while others might prefer to take a seat in a cozy chair in a different area of the room.

To facilitate collaborative project work among students, consider rearranging desks into U-shaped groups or pods. Students can study in a creative atmosphere if we increase the classroom's adaptability.

Creating a classroom library is a great approach to give students quick access to books that will improve their reading comprehension and inspire original thought. For kids who do not have easy access to a public library or books of their own, a classroom library can be a valuable resource. Books that support the class's creative learning activities might be added to a teacher's library.

Open-ended assignments: Allow students to exercise their creative instincts by substituting assignments that have a single correct answer with those that offer multiple ways of discovering a solution.

Seek alternatives to rote memorization: deprioritize memorization-focused tasks and replace them with tasks that allow students to challenge assumptions. Try

rewording assignments to promote creativity by adding phrases like “suppose” or “imagine.”

Work in groups :two heads are better than one. Groups tend to find more creative solutions as well as foster a sense of collaboration. This can provide a low-stakes environment to make students more comfortable exercising their creativity and also cognizant of each member of the group’s individual strengths and how those strengths can be leveraged to solve a problem in a unique way.

Giving feedback: giving creative feedback is one of the simpler ways to stimulate creative thinking, which can make it easy to overlook. Students with enormously creative solutions may not realize the value of their creativity unless a teacher articulates why their solutions are so effective. Peer feedback can also be useful and help students recognize the value of their creativity, too. Educators can set guidelines for how students can offer constructive feedback in ways that will be well received and helpful to their classmates.

Take advantage of curiosity: students have countless curiosities about the world that they’re eager to explore. Leverage their intrinsic motivation to learn by giving them opportunities to choose their own topics while learning and sharing that knowledge with the class.

Learner-centered: modern teaching methods are designed to focus on learners and keep them from being treated as denominators in classroom interactions, especially within the realm of basic science and technology curriculum.

Task-Based or Activity-Based: modern teaching methods instruct students through activities and specialized tasks to broaden their education and point of view.

Resource-Based: Teachers utilizing modern teaching methods are often dedicated to nurturing the resourcefulness of their students by encouraging the use of different, helpful project materials.

Interactive in Nature: one of the most vital characteristics of modern teaching methods is that tasks, projects, and problems are often interactive.

Peer Collaboration: Modern teaching methods don’t just encourage students to learn from educators but also from their peers. Peer collaboration ensures students receive all of the attention and feedback they need.

Blended learning: the next teaching method we’ll be exploring is blended learning. Essentially, blended learning is a combination of traditional face-to-face learning and technology-based learning. Using a blended learning model can be great for both students and teachers because it forms a middle ground between traditional and technology-based methods. It uses enough technology to keep students focused and interested, but it also provides opportunities for students to talk in-person to teachers and fellow classmates, which can be invaluable.

Student-centered learning: you can probably guess what this approach focuses on your students. While the success and happiness of students is always a high priority for teachers, student-centered learning is different to more traditional teaching methods.

In student-centered learning approaches, students are encouraged to take an active role in the classroom, rather than taking part in more passive activities like listening

to a lecture or writing an essay. They will have lots of discussions with their peers and teachers, and they'll also be encouraged to ask questions, which is linked to inquiry-based learning.

Teacher-centered learning :which is more common, requires the teacher to give classroom instructions and lead the class for the majority of the time. With student-centered learning, students are given more opportunities to choose what they want to learn and how they want to learn it. This is also known as personalized learning.

Discussion. Modern teaching, in essence, is a particular teaching method that focuses on instructing students to improve their intellect by utilizing new and innovative ideas, as opposed to making them recite information memorized from a syllabus to pass a rigid examination. Modern teaching focuses on the entire learning process, rather than focusing strictly on the final result, and is dedicated to helping students build skills as part of a constructivist approach to learning. Modern teaching methods are necessary because they help meet the educational needs of students in the contemporary era. It also focuses specifically on expanding their fundamental knowledge about the world and building critical thinking skills that will allow them to handle all kinds of challenges as they advance in their academic careers.

Conclusion. In conclusion, teachers can contribute significantly contribution to the improvement of the education system and collaborative learning environments. Encouraging teamwork among students can enhance engagement and academic performance. Suggesting the incorporation of modern teaching methods, such as creative and modern teaching methods, can make lessons more interactive and relevant. These all modern teaching methods will help to the future generations to be creative which means to be able to look at a broader picture and see the world in a new light.

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